

Controlling Free Volume in OSN Membranes via CPP Incorporation and THF-Mediated Interfacial Polymerization

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Abstract

The permeability–selectivity trade-off challenge in Organic solvent nanofiltration (OSN) membranes require accurate control over pore structure maintaining stability in aggressive solvents. In this work, polyamide thin-film composite membranes were synthesized via interfacial polymerization by incorporating cycloparaphenylene (CPP) as a porogen and tetrahydrofuran (THF) as a co-solvent to regulate reaction kinetics and network formation. CPP loading and THF content were adjusted and results revealed that an optimal composition (0.1 wt% CPP and 5% THF) shows a significant increase in solvent permeance without compromising the rejection. Morphological characterization by SEM and AFM confirmed the development of a more interconnected nodular structure with controlled roughness, while cross-sectional analysis indicated active layer thickness was reduced. In contrast, excessive CPP and THF induced interfacial instability and defect formation, resulting in reduced selectivity. The optimized membrane demonstrated stable performance in methanol filtration, maintaining 96% rejection of Congo Red with slight flux decline over.

Keywords: *Organic solvent nanofiltration, Free-volume controlling, Cycloparaphenylene, Tetrahydrofuran, Polyamide membrane.*

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Introduction

Organic solvent nanofiltration (OSN) is a pressure-driven membrane technology that separates solutes in the range of 100–1000 g/mol from organic solvents (Wang et al., 2023). Comparing to distillation and chromatography, OSN membrane shows a low-energy alternative in pharmaceutical, petrochemical and fine-chemical industries (Xiao et al., 2024; Halloub & Kujawski, 2025; Dorrington, 2020; Niu et al., 2026). The core of an OSN membrane is forming ultrathin selective layer, where a network of nano sized pores rules both solvent permeance and solute rejection. controlling these pores has developed as the central design challenge for next-generation OSN membranes (Lin et al., 2021; Abdulhamid & Szekely, 2022).

unlike aqueous nanofiltration, OSN must support robust pore architecture in aggressive solvents. Minor changes in pore size at the nanoscale can improve the performance of an OSN membrane from one with high permeability and low selectivity into a molecular sieve with improve permeate flux (Akbar Heidari & Mahdavi, 2023; Marchetti et al., 2017). The solvent resistance besides the permeance-rejection trade-off pushed pore engineering strategies beyond simple constriction. Many research studied involving the design of microporous polymers of intrinsic porosity, tuning the cross-linking density of polyimide or polyamide active layers, obtaining 2D materials with sub-nanometer interlayer channels, and utilizing

organized structures such as Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) and Covalent Organic Frameworks (COFs) capable of defining pore size. For example, Suzana research team (Wang et al., 2019) created dual-spacing membranes by By intercalating silica nanoparticles into graphene oxide. This hierarchical channel design effectively overcomes the classic permeance-rejection trade-off where the permeance of methanol reached $290 \text{ L m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ bar}^{-1}$ with 90% rejection of dyes more than 1.5 nm. Michael Z. Hu et.al. (2019) developed high-performance TFC membranes by incorporating COF nanoparticles into the polyamide layer. This method improved ethanol permeance by 46.7% to reach $79.8 \text{ L m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ MPa}^{-1}$ while achieving 99.4% dye rejection (479 Da). Last but not least, in our previous work, a poly-TaDb nanofiltration membrane was designed that utilizes metal-ion binding to enhance network structure. Specifically, Fe^{3+} coordination optimizes void size, the permeance of organic solvent increased significantly while maintaining high dye rejection proficiency compared to pristine membranes (Almijbilee et al., 2021).

In this article, improving OSN performance by engineering the porosity using cycloparaphenylene CPP was studied. First, interfacial polymerization conditions with the resulting pore-size distribution, solvent flux, and molecular weight cut-off were researched. Then, the sonication and utilizing tetrahydrofuran THF as cosolvent were investigated. To understand how CPP effect the membrane structure and membrane performance SEM, AFM and contact angle technologies were used for characterization. Finally, the long-term stability of these engineered pores in aggressive solvents was evaluate for scaling the fabrication process, laying out a practical pathway to OSN membranes that operate closer to the permeability–selectivity limit (scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Controlled Free Volume by Adjust CPP and THF Amount

Experimental Section

Materials

Polyetherimide (PEI, ULTEM 1000) was used as the support polymer. m-Phenylenediamine ($\geq 99\%$) and Trimesoyl chloride (TMC) ($\geq 98\%$) supplied from (Tianjin heowns Biochemical Technology Co., Ltd.) were used for interfacial polymerization. Cycloparaphenylene (CPP) was used as a porogen purchased from (Shanghai Aladdin Biochemical Technology Co., Ltd). Hexane was used as the organic solvent, and tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as a co-solvent provided from Tianjin heowns Biochemical Technology Co., Ltd. Ethylenediamine (EDA) was used as a crosslinking agent from Tianjin Kemiou Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. All chemicals were used as received without further purification. Deionized (DI) water was used throughout.

Preparation of Crosslinked PEI Support

PEI was dissolved in N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAc) to form a casting solution. 21 wt% stirred at 60 °C for 6 h, left overnight at room temperature for degassing. The solution casted onto a nonwoven polypropylene substrate using a 200 µm casting knife and immediately immersed in a DI water coagulation bath to induce phase inversion. For crosslinking PEI, the membrane immersion in 6% ethylenediamine (EDA) aqueous solution for 2 h at room temperature. After crosslinking, the membrane was washed with DI water to remove excess EDA and stored in water prior to interfacial polymerization (Zhou et al., 2021).

Preparation of OSN membrane by interfacial polymerization

Firstly, the organic phase was prepared by dissolving TMC (0.1 wt%) in hexane. CPP was added at different concentrations (0–0.20 wt%) into the organic phase in the present of THF (3–12 vol%) as a co-solvent to improve solubility and dispersion of CPP. The solution was sonicated for 15–20 min and mildly heated 35 °C to ensure homogeneous dispersion. The aqueous phase consisted of MPD (2 wt%) dissolved in DI water. The solution was stirred until complete dissolution and used immediately. The crosslinked PEI support membrane was first immersed in the organic phase for 2 min, then contacted with the aqueous phase containing MPD for 1 min to form interfacial polymerization. A thin polyamide selective layer was formed at the interface. After reaction the membrane was cured in an oven at 70 °C for 10 min to enhance crosslinking.

Membrane Characterization

Morphology

Surface and cross-sectional morphologies were characterized using Hitachi (Japan) S4800 scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Agilent 5500 Atomic force microscopy (AFM) was used to analyze surface topography and roughness in tapping mode.

Contact Angle

Water contact angles were measured using KINO SL200KB goniometer to evaluate surface hydrophilicity.

OSN Performance Evaluation

Organic solvent nanofiltration performance was evaluated using a cross-flow filtration system. The membrane washed by feeding THF solvent before feeding the evaluation solution to remove any residual CPP or undesirable matter. The effective membrane area 38.5 cm². Operating pressure 40 bar. The solvent permeance (J) was calculated as following Eq.1 (Almijbilee et al., 2020):

$$J = \frac{V}{A \cdot t \cdot P} \quad (1)$$

where V is permeate volume, A is membrane area, t is time, and P is applied pressure.

Solute Rejection and MWCO

Rejection experiments were conducted using organic dyes with molecular weights ranging from 300 to 1200 Da.

Rejection (R) was calculated as Eq. 2 (Almijbilee et al., 2020):

$$R(\%) = \left(1 - \frac{C_p}{C_f}\right) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where C_p and C_f are solute concentrations in permeate and feed, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Surface and Cross-Sectional Morphology (SEM)

The SEM top-surface images (Fig. 1, M0–M3) show the characteristic nodular (“ridge-and-valley”) morphology of polyamide layers formed via interfacial polymerization. The control membrane (M0, 0 wt% CPP) exhibits a dense and relatively uniform nodular structure, indicative of a highly crosslinked film. With the introduction of CPP, a progressive increase in nodular size and surface heterogeneity is observed. M1 (0.05 wt% CPP) shows slight enlargement of nodules while maintaining uniform coverage, suggesting well-dispersed CPP and minimal disruption of interfacial reaction. M2 (0.10 wt% CPP) exhibits more pronounced nodular features and increased interconnectivity, indicating enhanced free-volume formation within the polyamide network. M3 (0.20 wt% CPP) reveals significant coarsening which related to CPP aggregation (Li et al., 2025), which may lead to non-selective voids. Cross-sectional SEM images further confirm that the polyamide layer thickness decreases from 120 nm M0 to 80 nm M3, a thinning attributed to the presence of THF and CPP, which smooth monomer diffusion and reduce the effective reaction resistance at the interface. While moderate thinning M1 and M2 contributes to enhanced permeance, excessive thinning. M3 has flexible selectivity due to defect formation.

Figure 1. Surface and Cross-Section SEM Images of OSN Membrane Prepared at Different CPP% (M0: 0, M1: 0.01, M2: 0.05, M3: 0.1, M4: 0.2%)

Fig.2 shows AFM analysis provides quantitative insight into surface evolution upon CPP incorporation. M0 shows an RMS 18.2 nm and a smooth, compact surface; M1 yields RMS 20.1 nm with slight roughening; M2 gives RMS 22.3 nm and a well-developed nodular architecture; and M3 exhibits a highly rough and irregular surface with RMS 30.4 nm. The increase in roughness correlates with SEM observations and reflects progressive disruption of chain packing due to CPP addition (Yung et al., 2010), where at low concentrations (M1–M2) CPP is likely molecularly dispersed, creating uniform sub-

nanometer free-volume elements without generating macroscopic defects, while the sharp roughness increase in M3 indicates loss of structural control consistent with aggregation phenomena. Phase imaging further provides evidence of material heterogeneity within the selective layer: the control membrane (M0) exhibits a relatively uniform phase contrast consistent with a homogeneous polyamide network, whereas upon CPP addition, M1–M2 show slight phase contrast variations that indicate localized differences in mechanical properties attributed to CPP-induced free volume and remain finely distributed, supporting the formation of homogeneous pore structures, and M3 displays strong phase contrast with distinct domains, confirming phase separation and aggregation that likely translates into non-selective transport pathways.

Figure 2. AFM Surface Morphological and Mechanical Characterization of Membranes (M0–M3)

Water contact angle measurements show a decrease from 72° for M0 to 65° for M3 with increasing CPP content. This behavior is related to surface roughness, as described by the Wenzel model (Li et al., 2021):

$$\cos\theta^* = r\cos\theta \quad (3)$$

Since the polyamide membrane surface is moderately hydrophilic, increased roughness enhances wettability. The absence of a significant drop in contact angle indicates that CPP does not modify the surface chemistry but changes the surface morphology. This tendency is fully consistent with AFM roughness and SEM nodular growth.

Transport Performance and MWCO

Membrane performance was evaluated in OSN using dye molecules (300–1000 Da) (Imbrogno et al., 2025). The permeance increase for 0.1 wt% CPP, with only a modest MWCO shift, indicating successful free-volume engineering. At higher loading, a sharp increase in MWCO indicates loss of selectivity due to defect formation.

Figure 3. The Performance of OSN Membrane Prepared by 0.1% TMC and 2% MPD in the Present of Various CPP Ratios. Methanol as Solvent under 40 bar for 2h

THF plays a critical role in regulating CPP dispersion and interfacial polymerization. Moderate THF ($\leq 5\%$) improves CPP dispersion and enhances flux without compromising selectivity, whereas higher concentrations induce interfacial instability. THF plays a critical role in regulating CPP dispersion and interfacial polymerization. Moderate THF ($\leq 8\%$) improves CPP dispersion and enhances permeance without sacrificing selectivity, whereas higher concentrations of THF 8-12 % induce interfacial instability (Wang et al., 2023).

Figure 4. The Performance of OSN Membrane Prepared by 0.1% TMC, 2% MPD and 0.1% CPP Ratios with Different THF Percentage. Methanol as Solvent under 40 Bar for 2h

THF enhances monomer diffusion and improves CPP dispersion (Griwatz et al., 2023), resulting in a thinner polyamide layer with increased free volume and well-defined pore structures. This leads to an increase in solvent permeance while maintaining high solute rejection. However, at higher THF concentrations, excessive interfacial mixing disrupts the polymerization process, leading to structural defects and non-selective void formation. Consequently, although permeance increases further, membrane selectivity deteriorates sharply, indicating a transition from controlled pore formation to defect-dominated transport.

Long Term Performance of OSN Membrane

The long-term stability of the optimized membrane (0.1 wt% CPP, 5% THF) was assessed over 72 h using 30 ppm Congo Red dye (MW 696 Da) in methanol solvent under 40 bar. The membrane showed accepted stability, with only a slight decline in permeance about 4% during the test period. Meanwhile, solute rejection remained nearly constant at 96%, indicating the absence of defect formation or structural degradation.

The slight permeance reduction can be attributed to compaction or solvent-induced relaxation during the initial stage. The stable rejection further confirms that the pore structure and free-volume in the selective layer remained unbroken under test conditions. This behavior demonstrates that the incorporation of CPP at optimal loading, combined with optimum THF ratio.

Figure 5. Long-Term Test Performance of OSN Membrane Prepared by 0.1% TMC, 2% MPD, 0.1% CPP and 8% THF. Separation 30 ppm Congo Red Dye in Methanol under 40 Bar

Conclusion

Herein, a systematic approach was designed to adapt both the structure and performance of polyamide OSN membranes via the incorporation of a free-volume generator agent in combination with the co-solvent THF during interfacial polymerization. The results indicate that by incorporating CPP, it provides a controlled nano-scale free-volume elements, while THF serves an essential role to tune the monomer diffusion and interfacial reaction kinetics to establish the overall polymer network. At the proper THF content (5%), a polyamide, which is thinner yet similarly selective and more permeable than conventional

membranes. Higher THF result in interface instability and defects at the microscale level depending on precise control of process parameters.

The performance of optimized membrane (0.1 wt% CPP, 5% THF) was superior to other conditions in terms of combining high solvent permeance with stable rejection (96% congo red), Excellent long-term stability during continuous operation. Structural characterizations confirmed that the performance enhancement originated from controlled free-volume tuning instead of defect generation.

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